

Mechanism and Stoichiometry of the Reaction between Hg (II) and Iodide Ion

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One more attempt to work out a volumetric method for the determination of Hg(II) by iodide, suitable for a reasonable range of concentrations, proved futile, but the stoichiometry was very near 2:9 (HgCl₂ : KI) rather than 1:4 or 1:3 (reported by the previous workers). Analytical, conductometric, potentiometric and spectrophotometric measurements support the stoichiometry of 2:9(HgCl₂:KI).

Attempts to determine Hg(II) by iodide have been made by several workers in the past but without any success. It was with the intention of knowing the reason for this failure and the possible favourable conditions for a volumetric method that this work was taken up. The 'potentiometric method' seems to be the only one covering the wide range of concentrations of the reactants. The stoichiometry given by this method is 1:2 (HgCl₂ :KI) when iodide is completely precipitated. Koninck and Leburn¹ reported a possible volumetric estimation which as admitted by themselves, is attended with errors. Sasse² attempted to remove these errors and Kolthoff³ suggested corrections to be applied for different volumes of the reactants. Korenmann⁵ reported a method free from these corrections, but applicable to a very limited range of concentrations.

The difficulty encountered by the workers to obtain a suitable method lies in the fact that the precipitate of HgI₂ (pale yellow turning red) first formed dissolves in excess of iodide (HgCl₂ being added from the burette) forming a number of complexes. The type of complex formed depends to a large extent on the concentration of the reactants and the possibility of two or more complexes in equilibrium is not ruled out. These complexes have different dissociation constants, giving different equilibrium concentrations of iodide. The end point in any such volumetric estimation is marked by a permanent precipitate of red HgI₂ or pale yellow turbidity. Unfortunately, this permanent precipitate or turbidity appears at different HgCl₂ : KI stoichiometries in different concentrations of the reactants. The estimation of previous workers is based on the stoichiometry of 1 : 4 (HgCl₂ : KI). In fact, the permanent precipitate of HgI₂ for this stoichiometry would appear only for particular concentrations of reaction and for all other concentrations, a correction has to be applied as reported by Kolthoff³. If the solutions are concentrated the precipitate appears before sufficient mercury for 1:4 ratio is added and for dilute solutions (<0.003 M) the precipitate appears only after some more Hg(II) than that required by

1. Kolthoff and Furman, "Potentiometric Titrations", 1931.
2. De Koninck, *Bull. Assocn, Belgs.*, 1902, 127.
3. Sasse, *Chem. Zeit.*, 1920, 65, 559; *Chem. Abstr.*, 1920, 14, 1946.
4. Kolthoff, *Pharm. Weekblad*, 1920, 57, 836.
5. Korenmann, *Mikrochimie*, 1914, 14, 181.

1:4 complex, is added. The estimation suggested by Korenmann³ is based on the stoichiometry of 1 : 3 (HgCl_2 :KI) and is recommended for 0.003 molar solutions. No one had covering a wide range of concentrations could be worked out. However, a mechanistic information has been obtained and the results are presented in this paper.

The change at the end point is reversible, i.e., HgCl_2 may be titrated against iodide from the burette. The addition of iodide would first cause the complete precipitation of Hg(II) as iodide which subsequently dissolves if further quantities of iodide are added from the burette. The end point may be marked by the disappearance of the last trace of the red HgI_2 for concentrations greater than 0.005 *M*.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials: All the chemicals used were either BDH (analytical grade) or E. Merck (guaranteed reagents) quality. Mercuric nitrate may also be used in place of Mercuric chloride.

Titrations: Both types of titrations (appearance or disappearance of the white or red turbidity) were performed as said earlier.

Potentiometric Measurements: A tri-iodide-iodide ion couple was made by mixing 5 ml of a 2% iodine solution in alcohol with 20 ml of iodide solution. Platinum electrode dipping in this solution was joined to a calomel electrode through an agar-agar potassium chloride bridge. Titration was carried out by adding mercuric chloride from a burette. Bajaj Kaycee make potentiometer was used. Iodine concentration used was arbitrary as only qualitative behaviour of the system was required to be found out.

Conductometric Measurements: Iodide solutions were titrated conductometrically using Philips PR 9500 conductivity bridge at 50 cycles. A dipping cell was employed. The observations with large proportions of Hg(II) than in 2 : 9 (HgCl_2 : KI) complex, are not much reliable because HgI_2 was precipitated which had the tendency to get adsorbed at the platinum electrodes.

Spectrophotometric Measurement: These measurements were made by DU Beckman G 2400 Spectrophotometer in the wavelength region from 200 to 300 $\text{m}\mu$ and also at 335, 350 and 380 $\text{m}\mu$. The concentrations of iodide ion and HgCl_2 used were of the order of 1×10^{-3} molar for the range 200-300 $\text{m}\mu$. Higher concentrations of iodide indicated infinite optical density. Measurements with mixtures were also made in this region. Mixtures in higher concentration range (5×10^{-3} to 1×10^{-2} *M*) were studied in the wavelength range 240-380 $\text{m}\mu$. These mixtures were pale yellow. Iodide showed almost no absorption and mercuric chloride little absorption in this range. Absorption curve for mixture showed a shoulder at 288 $\text{m}\mu$ when iodide was in excess. When, however, both the reactants were in comparable concentrations, the shoulder was indicated at 263 $\text{m}\mu$. Job's method was applied at 288 $\text{m}\mu$ to find out the molar ratio of the reactants in the complex. For higher concentrations of the reactants this was done at arbitrarily chosen wavelengths 335 and 350 $\text{m}\mu$ because infinite absorption was indicated at 263 or 288 $\text{m}\mu$.

DISCUSSION

The results of simple titrations indicate that if the concentrations of the reactants are 0.005 *M* or more the end point occurs at or very near the stoichiometry of 2 : 9 (HgCl₂ : KI) rather than 1:5, 1:4 or 1:3. In case HgCl₂ is taken in the burette the results in most cases are positive, not exceeding 6%. In case KI is taken in the burette, the results are both positive and negative (within 6%). Some of the results show that the stoichiometry changes from 2 : 9 to 1 : 4 or 1 : 3 down to 1 : 2 as the concentration of the reactants is changed. For concentrations below 0.0005 *M* no precipitate and hence no end point was marked. The formation of permanent precipitate or turbidity to mark the end point, depends on the concentrations of iodide and mercuric chloride both and, therefore, this excess of HgCl₂ required to form the precipitate or turbidity would always vary and the deviations of the results from the stoichiometry of 2 : 9 can be explained due to the dissociation of the complex, Hg₂I₉²⁻.

As mentioned earlier a number of complexes of Hg(II) and iodide ions may be formed. 1 : 4 (HgCl₂:KI) complex has been reported by a number of workers^{3,4,7-10} and definitive studies on HgI₄, HgI₃ and HgI₂ and HgI have been made by Sillen and coworkers. 1:3 complex has been reported by others also^{6,11,12}. However, on the basis of physical measurements carried out in this investigation it can be said that in presence of excess of iodide 1:5 (HgI₃²⁻) complex is preferably formed. This dissociates according to the equation,

Equilibrium (1) gives the situation when HgCl₂ corresponding to 1:5 ratio has been added to the iodide. Further addition of HgCl₂ makes it to react with iodide of equilibrium (1) giving a precipitate which dissolves because sufficient iodide ion concentration is available from this equilibrium. Just before the end point the whole of the mercury practically exists in the complex Hg₂I₉²⁻ or 2HgCl₂·9KI in equilibrium with smaller (than in equilibrium (1) concentration of iodide ions:

Excess of HgCl₂ now reacts with iodide giving HgI₄ which may not dissolve for want of sufficient iodide ion concentration. However, this excess required may be quite large, if sufficient iodide ion concentration is available from equilibrium (2) because then the precipitate formed would dissolve. Such a situation is expected when we have a high concentration of the complex which on dissociation would give comparatively larger concentration of iodide ions. The complex HgI₄²⁻ in equilibrium (2) may also dissociate⁹ to give a lower complex HgI₃²⁻ and iodide, but the dissociation would be less than that of HgI₃²⁻ or Hg₂I₉²⁻.

If the reactants are dilute (0.005 *M* or less) the results are higher because the solubility product¹³ of HgI₂ may not be exceeded unless sufficient mercuric chloride from the

6. Brulley, *Ann. Chim. Phys.*, 1827, 34, 345.

7. Anerback and Plueddemann, *Arch. Kais. Gesund. Amt.*, 1909, 34, 178; *Chem. Abstr.*, 1910, 4, 2080.

8. Spacu and Spacu, *Z. anal. Chem.* 1932, 89, 187.

9. Job, *Compt. rend.*, 1925, 180, 1932; *Chem., Abstr.*, 1925, 19, 2788.

10. Sillen, *Acta. Chem. Scand.*, 1949, 3, 539; 1954 8, 299, 318.

11. Marah, *Jour. Chem. Soc.*, 1914, 105, 2368.

12. Galais, *Compt. rend.*, 1932, 193, 875; *Chem. Abstr.*, 1933, 27, 677.

13. Herz and Anders, *Zeit. anorg., Chem.* 1907, 52, 164; *Chem. Abstr.* 1907, 1, 955.

burette is added. The results indicate that the volume of $HgCl_2$ required is more and more if concentration of the reactants is gradually decreased. For 0.0005 molar solutions, the precipitate is not at all obtained even though the reactants may be mixed in the ratio of 1 : 2 ($HgCl_2:KI$).

It should, therefore, be clearly understood that the positive or negative results give only the situation when a precipitate is obtained and which depends on three factors:

1. Concentration of the complex which in turn controls the concentration of iodide ions. Positive results with concentration reactants (when $HgCl_2$ is in the burette) and negative results (when KI is in the burette) are obtained as a result of high concentration of the complex.
2. Solubility product of HgI_2 which can not being exceeded can account for positive results in case of dilute reactants.
3. The dissociation of $HgCl_2$ which controls the concentration of mercuric ions.

Conductivity data (Fig. 1) show the formation of two complexes, 1 : 5 and 2 : 9 ($HgCl_2:KI$). It is further noted that as the concentration of the reactants is decreased, the tendency of the formation of 1 : 5 complex decreases. Evidence for 2 : 9 complex has already been shown by Solanki and Joshi¹⁴ from viscosity and refractivity measurements.

Fig. 2 gives the potentiometric titration curves. The large potential variation shows the complete precipitation of iodide, but this portion of each curve is preceded by a small

FIG. 1

14. Solanki and Joshi, *Journ.* 1942, 19, 9.

FIG. 2

inflexion at a point corresponding to 2 : 9 complex. An inflexion point is observed, whenever, there is a different rate of change of potential as the concentration of the species affecting the electrode potential changes. The following equilibria will have to be considered, if we want to calculate the potential.

The potential at 25° at the platinum electrode is given by the equation,

$$E = 0.54 + 0.059 \log \frac{[I_3^-]}{[I^-]}$$

The potential depends mainly on iodide ion concentration because iodine concentration was in excess and hence constant. As the iodide ions are removed by complex formation, the potential rises fairly uniformly till the formation of 1 : 5 complex is complete. Beyond this stage the rate of increase of potential is slightly greater because with the formation of 2 : 9 complex, only a small equilibrium concentration of iodide is available. Each drop of $HgCl_2$ added from the burette, therefore, brings about comparatively a greater rate of decrease of iodide ion concentration.

Spectrophotometric results do not provide much information about these complexes. In the range a 200-300 $m\mu$ iodide absorbs with a peak at 225 $m\mu$ and a minimum of 210 $m\mu$ (figures not shown). Concentrations employed were $1.5 \times 10^{-5} M$. $HgCl_2$ of this concentration does not absorb. Complexes of these two reactants, if any formed, do not seem to absorb because the characteristic absorption curve of iodide is little changed by the presence of $HgCl_2$. The optical density of the mixtures, which is due to iodide ions, decreases at 225 $m\mu$ obviously because the complex is formed. The absorbance on the other hand, increases at 210 $m\mu$ showing thereby that the complex also absorbs at this wavelength. A pale yellow complex seems to be formed when the concentrations employed were of the order of $1 \times 10^{-3} M$. Measurements between 240-380 $m\mu$ show a shoulder at wavelength depending on the concentrations.

FIG. 3

FIG. 4

Job's¹⁵ continuous variation method could not be done beyond the (KI : HgCl₂) ratio of 3 : 1 because of the formation of the precipitate at this stage or even earlier. The only information available from this curve is that a break in the curve occurs when KI and HgCl₂ are in the ratio of 4.5:1. The break does not change its position with the change in the concentration of the reactants. There is very little shift of the break with the change in the wavelength. This indicates that only one absorbing complex is being formed¹⁶ and this is probably not 2 : 9 complex. The latter complex either does not absorb or the significantly low extinction coefficients. However, if the concentrations are low, Job's continuous variation method gave a peak at 1 : 3 (HgCl₂ : KI) complex with breaks at 1 : 4 and 1 : 4.5. Another method¹⁷ gave the complex formation of KI and HgCl₂ in the ratio of 1 : 2.

Spectroscopic evidence for 1 : 4 and 1 : 3 complexes has also been reported by Inoue¹⁸ and Job¹⁹.

Analytical evidence for the formation of 2 : 9 complex has been obtained in one more way. Mercuric chloride and iodide were mixed in such proportions that the precipitate formed does not dissolve completely. This was filtered and the filtrate made upto 100 ml. The residue and the filtrate were separately analysed for mercury content by Rupp's¹⁹ iodometric method. Samples of filtrate were titrated also against HgCl₂ to the red or white turbidity end point. The results are shown in tables I and II.

TABLE I
HgCl₂ (taken=10 ml of 0.05M = 135.75 mgm of Hg.

Mixture (HgCl ₂ + KI) No.	KI 0.05M ml.	Residue			Filtrate		0.01HgCl ₂ required for another sam- ple of 25 ml of filtrate ml.
		KIO ₃ added 0.01M ml	Excess of KIO ₃ found in ml of 0.02N Na ₂ S ₂ O ₃	Volume taken ml	KIO ₃ added 0.01M ml	Excess of KIO ₃ found in ml of 0.02N Na ₂ S ₂ O ₃	
A	25	20	22.60	25	10	27.80	0.25
B	30	20	30.00	25	10	25.70	0.20
C	35	20	41.45	25	10	22.80	0.10
D	40	10	22.10	25	10	20.00	0.05
E	44	10	29.40	25	10	18.00	0.05

TABLE II

Mixture (HgCl ₂ +KI) No.	Hg Found in resi- due mgm	Hg found in fil- trate mgm	mgm of Hg expected in the filtrate if the whole of KI forms complex in molar ratio			Total Hg (residue+fil- trate) found mgm
			2:9	1:4	1:5	
A	102.85	24.42	27.15	93.99	22.62	127.27
B	82.50	47.52	54.9	67.87	45.24	130.02
C	51.05	79.20	81.45	101.79	67.86	130.25
D	21.80	110.00	108.6	135.75	90.48	131.80
E	1.65	130.00	130.2	—	108.60	131.63

15. Job, *Ann. Chim.*, 1928, 9, 113; *Chem. Abstr.*, 1928, 22, 2120.

16. Vosburgh and Cooper. *Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 63, 437.

17. Bent and French. *Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 63, 568.

18. Inoue, *J. Chem. Soc.*, Japan, 1927, 48, 1.

19. Rupp, *Art. Pharm.*, 1905, 248, 300.

It can be seen that the mercury content in the filtrate corresponds to the 2:9 complex. The formation of 1:4 complex seems to be far fetched. In cases D and E iodide is sufficient to dissolve the whole of the precipitate to form HgI_4^{2-} , but the fact the dissolution of HgI_4 is not complete, suggests that this complex is little formed. From mixtures A and B it appears that both the complexes HgI_3^{2-} and $\text{Hg}_2\text{I}_9^{5-}$ are formed. This is further supported by the fact that the filtrate A and B require 0.25 and 0.20 ml of 0.01M HgCl_2 for titration to the red end point (corresponding to 2:9 stoichiometry) because as said earlier, HgI_3^{2-} complex alone would do so where as the 2:9 complex may give a red precipitate with even a drop of 0.01M HgCl_2 .

The total mercury content found was always somewhat less than the theoretical value (135.75 mgm), but very nearly equal to the value found (132.10 mgm). Slightly low values in some cases might be due to the difficulty in dissolving the mercuric iodide residue on the filter paper. However, we are here concerned only with the filtrate where we have the expected results.

It is, therefore, very probable that a 2:9 complex is formed and the end point of the filtration to which previous workers refer nearly corresponds to this stoichiometry and not 1:4. Our results indicate that in the concentration range 0.2-0.005M the percentage deviation would be more if we assume the stoichiometry of 1:4.

Though it has not been possible to give a volumetric method for the determination of Hg (II) by iodide for a reasonable range of concentrations, the results are within 5% if we assume the stoichiometry of 2:9 (HgCl_2 :KI). Where accuracy is not of much importance this method may be of help to us, particularly when the other methods²⁰⁻²⁴ are time-consuming and involve a number of operations. This titration, if we were to do it, can be carried out in presence of iodate and bromate. The iodometric method^{19,25,26} would not work in these cases. Other substances which do not affect the results of this titration are bromide, chloride, Mg^{++} , Zn^{++} , Al^{3+} , HNO_3 , HClO_4 and H_2SO_4 .

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